

LONG-TERM DURABILITY TESTING OF TOKYO ROPE CARBON CABLES

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ABSTRACT

Long-term behavior of composite materials is still a controversial issue among the engineering community though fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) reinforcements are increasingly used in infrastructure applications. The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of different environmental conditions on the long-term behavior of Tokyo Rope carbon-fiber composite cables (CFCCs) subjected to tensile load. Specimens were exposed to alkaline solutions for 1000, 3000, 5000, and 7000 hours at elevated temperature (60°C) to accelerate the effect of the concrete environment. The alkali exposure condition was based on CSA S806 [1], and ACI 440 [2]. The durability performance of the Tokyo Rope CFCC tendons was assessed by conducting tensile tests on the specimens after different exposure periods. The test results revealed that the average tensile-strength retentions of the conditioned CFCCs could be affected with accelerated time and temperature in alkaline solutions. While some experimental work on characterizing the durability of CFCC has been completed, other studies are still ongoing at the University of Sherbrooke, such as the effect of alkaline conditioning under prestressing load.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Corrosion of steel reinforcement in concrete bridges subjected to deicing salts and/or aggressive environments constitutes the major cause of structure deterioration, leading to costly repairs and rehabilitation as well as a significant reduction in service life. In the last decade, the use of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) as an alternative reinforcing material in reinforced and prestressed concrete (RC) structures has emerged as an innovative solution to the corrosion problem [3]. The proven track record of superior performance of FRP materials in terms of strength, durability, resistance to corrosion, and versatility of fabrication have made these materials attractive to civil engineers. FRP bars and tendons have been used successfully as main reinforcement in concrete bridges, parking garages, tunnels, and water tanks [4]. Therefore, the development of reinforced concrete with FRP bars and tendons and their application in infrastructure is gaining considerable interest in the civil-engineering community.

Long-term behavior of composite materials is still a controversial issue among the engineering community though FRP reinforcements are increasingly used in infrastructure applications. Concrete is highly alkaline due to the high calcium hydroxide content of hardened cement stone (pH 12.5 to 14) that needs special attention for durability of FRP reinforcements. Numerous studies have been conducted to assess the durability of FRP reinforcement for reinforced concrete structures [5]. The majority of these studies has highlighted on the short-term performance of FRP bars. Moreover, most of these studies have investigated the durability characteristics of glass-FRP bars for reinforced concrete structures. On the other hand, the durability of carbon FRP reinforcement for reinforced or prestressed concrete structures has not been yet thoroughly investigated or found in the literature and hence reliable design rules for RC structures are still lacking.

The experimental study reported here is part of an ongoing comprehensive research project at the University of Sherbrooke (Sherbrooke, Quebec, Canada) in collaboration with the University of North Florida (Jacksonville, FL, USA), and North Carolina State University (Raleigh, NC, USA), through the "Degradation Assessment of Internal Continuous Fiber Reinforcement in Concrete Environment" research project funded by the Florida Department of Transportation (FDOT). The program includes experimental and analytical research to investigate the physical, mechanical, and durability characteristics of FRP reinforcement for non-prestressing and prestressing concrete applications. The variables include different exposure conditions (marine and alkaline environments), fiber type (carbon, glass, and basalt), with or without sustained load, elevated temperature (22°C, 40°C, 50°C, and 60°C), and exposure time (1000, 3000, 5000, and 7000 hours). The research program is designed to be conducted in three main phases: Phase 1 is characterization of physical and mechanical properties; Phase 2, durability evaluation with and without load; and Phase 3, structural testing of concrete members reinforced with FRP. This paper represents a summary of the preliminary Phase-1 study on the physical properties of Tokyo Rope carbon-fiber composite cable (CFCC) tendons. In addition, part of the Phase-2 test results on the degradation of the tensile properties of CFCC tendons (diameter: 7.5 mm) exposed to alkaline solution (pH 12.5 to 13) without sustained load is presented.

2 MATERIALS OF CARBON FRP CABLE

The carbon-fiber composite cables (CFCCs) manufactured by Tokyo Rope Manufacturing Co. Ltd., Japan, were used. This type of reinforcement is of interest to the Florida Department of Transportation and other DOTs for use as corrosion-resistant reinforcing material for prestressed precast-concrete bridge-deck and pile applications (as a competitive material of stainless-steel prestressing cables). The Tokyo Rope carbon-fiber composite cable is a stranded cable made from a number of individual rods. In general, these cables are made of 7, 19, or 37 twisted carbon rods, with nominal diameters varying from 5 to 40 mm (0.2 to 1.6 in.). The individual rods are made with carbon fibers impregnated with thermosetting resin. In this study, CFCC cables 7.5 mm and 12.5 mm in diameter made with a 7-rod strand are used, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CFCC Rope (1x7 7.5 mm)

3 CHARACTERISATION OF PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Physical and microstructural analyses were conducted on CFCC tendons 12.5 mm in diameter as a preliminary investigation of this material's performance. Physical properties included: (1) carbon-fiber content, (2) water absorption, (3) cure ratio, and (4) glass-transition temperature. These properties were determined out according to CSA S807 [6]. Moreover, optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electronic microscopy (SEM) analyses were performed to investigate the material's microstructure.

The test results indicated that the carbon-fiber content in weight of CFCC was 82.0%. The mass percentage of water uptake after 24 hours and at saturation were found to be 0.8% and 1.1% on average. The water-absorption values obtained exceed the limits specified in CSA S807 [6]. The material's cure ratio is high (close to 100%). The glass transition temperature was not clearly visible from the thermograms obtained by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), two very small shifts were observed at 110° and 150°C, approximately. However, it was not possible to confirm that these shifts are caused by the glass transition of one, two or a blend of resins.

Figures 2 to 5 present OM micrographs of the cross section of a cable sample. Figure 2 provides a general view of the seven strands. Each strand was covered with a layer of polyester fibers. The intersection between the central and outer strands created six voids along the cable. Some pores are visible at various degrees, as shown in Figures 3 and 4 for two distinct strands. Figure 5 is a close-up of the intersection between two strands, revealing a few voids in the coating.

Figure 2: General view of the seven strands

Figure 3: View of strand 1

Figure 4: View of strand 2

Figure 5: Close-up of the intersection between 2 strands

Figures 6 to 9 show SEM micrographs of transverse and longitudinal sections of the sample. A large pore was found in a SEM micrograph at the intersection of two strands as shown in Figure 6. Figure 7 clearly shows the tubular shape of the pores in the cross section of a strand. A cross section of a strand at medium magnification is shown in Figure 8. The bonding between the carbon fibers and the thermosetting resin is good since there were no free gaps at the interface. However, sporadic debonding may occur, as evidenced in Figure 9, which was obtained at high magnification.

Figure 6: SEM micrograph at the intersection

Figure 7: View of tubular shape of the pores

Figure 8: Cross section of a strand at medium magnification

Figure 9: Debonding at the interface

4 DURABILITY EVALUATION WITHOUT LOAD

4.1 Environmental Conditions

The CFCC cable having 7.5 mm in diameter (area of 31.1 mm²) with a 7-rod strand was received as one coil. All bars prepared for tensile preloading were cut into lengths of 1600 mm as specified in ASTM D7205 [7]. The bars were divided into two series: (1) the unconditioned control samples and (2) the conditioned samples immersed in alkaline solution. The CFCC specimens were completely immersed in alkaline solution inside different PVC tubes. The alkaline solution was prepared using calcium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide, and sodium hydroxide (118.5 g of Ca(OH)₂ + 0.9 g of NaOH + 4.2 g of KOH in 1 L of deionized water) according to CSA S806 [1] and ACI 440 [2]. The alkali solution's pH was 12.8. The tubes and CFCC specimens were kept at 60°C. Environmental chamber was used to accelerate the degradation of the CFCC specimens at 60°C, as shown in Figure 10. The immersion temperature was chosen to accelerate the degradation effect of aging, but it was not high enough to produce any thermal-degradation mechanisms. The specimens were removed from the

alkaline solution after 1000, 3000, 5000, and 7000 hours. Table 1 provides a summary of the environmental conditioning and the number of samples used for the durability study.

a. The environmental chamber

b. Specimens inside the environmental room

Figure 10 : Environmental conditioning chamber

Table 1 : Test program of CFCC specimens

Time of Immersion (hour)	Temperature (°C)	Number of Specimens
0	22	5
1000	60	3
3000	60	3
5000	60	3
7000	60	3

4.2 CFCC Specimen Preparation and Tensile Test

All of the control and conditioned CFCC specimens were tested under tension according to ASTM D7205 [7]. The CFCC specimen length as well as the length and diameter of the anchor to be used for the tensile test were calculated according to ASTM D7205 [7]. The test specimens were instrumented with one linear variable differential transformer (LVDT, 200 mm length) to capture specimen elongation during testing. The tests were carried out with the Baldwin testing machine in the structures laboratory of the Department of Civil Engineering at the University of Sherbrooke, (see Figure 11). The rate of loading was 560 MPa/min. The applied load and bar elongation were recorded during the test with a computer data-acquisition system.

5 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Retention of Tensile Properties

Table 2 gives the average, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, and retention values for the tensile strength, Young's modulus, and strain in the control and conditioned CFCC specimens. The average tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of the control specimens were 3154 MPa, and 15 GPa, respectively. The guaranteed tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of the tested CFCC cable

are set by the manufacturer to 2440 MPa, and 155 GPa, respectively. The results of average tensile strength obtained after conditioning for 1000, 3000, 5000, and 7000 hours at 60°C were 3077, 3067, 3014, and 2928 MPa, respectively. The corresponding values for the modulus of elasticity were 150.0, 148.1, 147.0, and 147.1 MPa, respectively.

Figure 11: Tensile test set-up

Evidently, the tensile strength of the conditioned CFCC specimens decreased as the immersion time increased. The tensile-strength retentions were about 97.6%, 97.2%, 95.6%, and 92.8% after 1000, 3000, 5000, and 7000 hours of immersion at 60°C, respectively. These results indicate that the strengths of the CFCC specimens were affected by increasing the immersion duration at higher temperature levels. On the other hand, the environmental conditioning slightly affected the elastic modulus of the aged CFCC specimens. Increasing the duration of immersion time from 1000 to 7000 hours decreased the elastic modulus approximately from 150 GPa to 147 GPa, respectively. Finally, the test results shown in Table 2 indicate that the strain-retention capacities were 98.6%, 99.5%, 98.6%, and 95.7%, after 1000, 3000, 5000, and 7000 hours of immersion at 60°C, respectively. The reduction of the tensile properties of the CFCC conditioned specimens could not be attributed to any significant degradation or reduction in carbon fibers tensile properties. The strength reduction of the conditioned specimens is instead due the interface fiber/resin degradation that reduces the stress transfer. Other studies such as SEM analyses are on-going to investigate the interface degradation of the Tokyo Rope Carbon Cable in alkaline environment and elevated temperatures.

Test results of Table 2 were used to predict the service life of the CFCC at mean annual temperatures (MATs) of 10°C and 50°C, using the procedure proposed by Bank et al. 2003. The temperature of 10°C corresponds well to northern regions MAT, while 50°C corresponds to MAT of warm regions such as in Middle East, and Florida. The tensile-strength retention obtained for a service life of 75 and 150 years at MAT of 10°C and 50°C correspond to 83% and 80%, and 78% and 75%, respectively. It is noted that these predictions are obtained using results of conditioned samples subjected to no stress; lower tensile strength retention values could be expected using data of samples subjected to stress under conditioning.

Table 2 :Tensile test results of the control and conditioned CFCC specimens

Time of Immersion (h)	Temperature (°C)	Tensile Strength (MPa)			Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)			Ultimate Strain (%)		
		Avg.	COV (%)	Retention (%)	Avg.	COV (%)	Retention (%)	Avg.	COV (%)	Retention (%)
0	22	3154	2.30	100	151.0	0.61	100	2.08	1.71	100
1000	60	3077	2.97	97.6	150.0	0.91	99.3	2.05	2.06	98.6
3000	60	3067	2.99	97.2	148.1	1.09	98.1	2.07	3.68	99.5
5000	60	30146	3.74	95.6	147.0	0.48	97.3	2.05	3.27	98.6
7000	60	2928	0.35	92.8	147.1	0.22	97.4	1.99	0.54	95.7

5.2 Mode of Failure

Due to the brittle nature of CFCC, no yielding occurred and the stress–strain behavior was linear. Figure 12 shows the typical failure mode of the CFCC. The test results indicate that the aging condition with alkaline solution at different temperatures did not affect the failure mode significantly.

Figure 12: Typical mode of failure

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper represented an overview on the physical, microstructural analyses, and preliminary durability characterization on CFCC cables. Unstressed CFCC specimens (7.5 mm diameter) were immersed in alkaline solution of pH 12.8 accelerated at elevated temperature (60°C) to simulate the effect of alkalinity in concrete. On the basis of the experimental physical and durability results the following conclusions were drawn:

1- The test observation indicated that the carbon fiber content is 82% by weight and the water uptake at saturation is equal to 1.1%. The cure ratio of the material is very high (close to 100%) but its glass transition temperature is not clearly visible by DSC.

2- Optical microscopy and electronic scanning microscopy analysis showed that strands presented various levels of porosity. However, no major defect was detected in the tested CFCC material.

3- The results indicate that the strengths of the CFCC specimens were affected by increasing the

immersion duration at higher temperature levels. After 7000 hour of immersion in the alkaline solution at 60°C, test result indicated that 7% degradation in the tensile strength occurred. The strength reduction was attributed to the interface degradation that could be caused by a sizing problem. Further investigations are required on this topic.

4- Using a procedure to predict the service life, the tensile-strength retention obtained for a service life of 75 years at MATs of 10oC and 50°C correspond to 83%, and 78%, respectively. More research is, however, needed to refine this service life prediction using more CFCC samples and different cable sizes.

5- Finally, durability characterization study of CFCC is underway to evaluate the effect of alkaline conditioning for long duration at different temperature and exposer conditions under different sustained tensile load (from 30 up to 75% of ultimate tensile load). This study is highly recommended to determine the critical stress (allowable) and safety factors for the use of this structural material as corrosion-resistant reinforcing material for prestressed precast-concrete bridge-deck and pile applications in Florida marine environment.

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